

MICROMECHANICAL MODELING OF FERRITIC/PEARLITIC NODULAR CAST IRON

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SUMMARY: One of the main factors in determining the different grades of ductile iron is the matrix structure. In the as-cast condition, the matrix will consist of varying proportions of pearlite and ferrite, and as the amount of pearlite increases, the strength and hardness of the iron also increase. Three different nodular cast irons are here considered and two alternative micromechanics modeling approaches are then introduced and applied to predict the experimental behavior i) an axisymmetric unit cell model and ii) a microstructural finite element model. Both models predict the change of mechanical response of nodular cast iron as a function of the ferrite-to-pearlite ratio in the matrix. The mechanical response of the axisymmetric unit cell model is stiffer than that of an equivalent microstructural finite element model.

KEYWORDS: nodular cast iron, tensile properties, microstructure, micromechanics, finite element method, unit cell.

INTRODUCTION

Nodular cast iron has strength, impact toughness and ductility comparable to those of many grades of steel, while far exceeding those of standard gray iron. In addition, nodular cast iron offers the same advantages of gray iron in terms of design flexibility and low cost casting procedures. Typical examples of nodular cast iron applications include valves, pumps, cylinder liners, crankshafts, metal working rolls, dies, gears and process equipment, [1].

The main factor in determining the different grades of ductile iron is the matrix structure. In the as-cast condition, the matrix will consist of varying proportions of pearlite and ferrite, and as the amount of pearlite increases, the strength and hardness of the iron also increase. On the other hand, as the amount of pearlite decreases, the maximum impact energy in the ductile condition increases, and the ductile-to-brittle transition temperature range falls, [1]. Therefore nodular cast iron can be considered a special kind of MMC in that graphite nodules are dispersed in a matrix, which itself can be a combination of ferrite and pearlite, [2].

The structure of the matrix is essentially determined by the cooling rate through the eutectoid temperature range. Slow cooling rates prevalent in heavy sections promote the transformation to ferrite. An increased graphite nodule number, achieved by better inoculation, tends also to increase the amount of ferrite. If a pearlitic matrix is desired, pearlite formers (such as copper) are added to the molten iron. Control of the chemical composition of the melt and of the casting process makes it possible to obtain a fully ferritic matrix structure characterized by

ductility up to 25% and a mechanical strength similar to low carbon steel. Alternatively, a fully pearlitic matrix can give a tensile strength up to 800 MPa but with low impact toughness and ductility, [1].

In practice, a matrix with both ferrite and pearlite with intermediate mechanical properties is often found and the present authors experimentally investigated nodular cast irons with a wide variety of ferrite/pearlite ratios, [3-5]. Fig. 1 presents typical microstructures revealed by etching that are characterized by three ferrite volume fractions.

Fig. 1: Microstructures of nodular cast iron with different content of ferrite in the matrix a) A; b) B; c) C

A thorough microstructural investigation was carried out on metallographic samples as reported in detail elsewhere, Tab. 1, [5]. Tensile strength, elongation to rupture, hardness, impact toughness and transition behavior were also determined in the presence of different ferrite/pearlite ratios, [3-5]. Hardness and strength increase and ductility decrease when ferrite content increases. Elongation to rupture shows a strong dependence on ferrite content. The mechanical properties for the three nodular cast irons of Fig. 1 are presented in Tab. 1.

Table 1: Microstructure and mechanical properties of the nodular cast irons shown in Fig. 1

NCI ↓	Graphite form	Ψ_G (%)	N (mm ⁻²)	Ψ_F (%)	σ_0 (MPa)	σ_u (MPa)	A%	KCO (J/cm ²)	HB
A	80%VI7+20%V7	15.0	174	93.5	350	535	15	90	178
B	70%VI6+30%V6	12.3	117	55.6	400	564	12	6	216
C	70%VI5+30%V7	9.8	96	15.3	450	770	6	11	221

In parallel, the present authors have been developing a micromechanical modeling activity aimed at describing the relationship between microstructure and mechanical properties of nodular cast iron. A micromechanical modeling approach based on the use of a unit cell was proposed in [6] and a direct correlation with experiments in terms of constitutive behavior presented. While the correlation was promising, further investigation of the potential of the finite element method to predict microstructure-affected constitutive behavior is carried out. An alternative approach starts with the direct generation of finite element models from micrographs of etched microstructures, the definition of suitable constitutive laws and boundary conditions to obtain a homogenized constitutive response, [7]. This paper reviews the main features of the two modeling approaches to assess their respective applicability.

UNIT-CELL MODELING APPROACH

This approach was initially applied to ferritic nodular cast iron in [2,8,9] and the present authors extended the approach to a ferritic/pearlitic matrix in [6]. In this approach, the microstructure is assumed to be periodic and resulting from the assembly of hexagonal units of equal size with a graphite nodule at their centers. The hexagonal cell is then approximated

by a circular cylinder to allow simple axisymmetric calculations, [2]. Fig. 2a shows that a pearlitic/ferritic nodular cast iron is characterized by graphite nodules enveloped by ferrite while pearlite fills the remaining volume. If graphite nodules are assumed perfectly periodic, the scheme of Fig. 2b is obtained. The axisymmetric unit cell is also shown in Fig. 2b.

Fig. 2: a) Pearlitic nodular cast iron etched with Nital 3% 100x; b) representative unit cell; c) axisymmetric finite element model

Only one quarter of the radial cross-section of the unit cell is modeled with four-node axisymmetric finite elements as shown in Fig. 2c. The cell model is characterized by a graphite nodule located at its center and by a concentric ferrite capsule surrounding it. Unit cell models for the three nodular cast iron of Tab. 1 are readily defined on the basis of the volume fraction of graphite and the fraction of ferrite in the matrix. The unit cell model is meshed using finite elements and on the base of symmetry arguments, the global behavior of the assembly is obtained by studying the response of the unit cell subjected to appropriate boundary conditions.

Three are the constituent materials in the models, namely graphite, ferrite and pearlite. The graphite can be considered isotropic and perfectly elastic with a symmetric Young's modulus (in tension and compression) $E = 15$ GPa and a Poisson ratio $\nu = 0.3$. The matrix constituents, ferrite and pearlite, are assumed to be described by the J_2 -flow theory of plasticity with isotropic hardening and von Mises yield condition. The uniaxial behavior of ferrite and pearlite is modeled as an elastic-plastic Ramberg-Osgood-type material, [7].

To investigate the mechanical response of the unit cell, a homogeneous displacement U_2 is applied in the axial direction to the Γ_1 boundary in Fig. 2c while the axial degrees of freedom of the bottom side nodes are suppressed. The nodule-to-matrix interface is modeled as a unilateral contact along the boundary surface Γ_0 boundary in Fig. 2c, while the ferrite-to-pearlite interface is infinitely strong. The radial displacement of the vertical boundary is homogeneous by constraint conditions to enforce periodic compatibility along Γ_2 boundary in Fig. 2c. The homogenized principal strains, E_i with $i = 1, 2, 3$, are given by

$$E_2 = \frac{U_2}{L_0}; \quad E_1 = E_3 = \frac{r - R_0}{R_0} \quad (1)$$

where r is the current value of the outer radius of the deformed unit cell. The corresponding homogenized principal stresses Σ_1 , Σ_2 and Σ_3 are computed integrating the reaction forces σ_{11} and σ_{22} , at the unit cell boundaries

$$\Sigma_1 = \Sigma_3 = \int_{\Gamma_2} \sigma_{11} d\Gamma_2 \quad \Sigma_2 = \int_{\Gamma_1} \sigma_{22} d\Gamma_1 \quad (2)$$

The axisymmetric unit cell model is obtained by simplification of a regular arrangement of hexagonal cells. Therefore, a preliminary verification of this hypothesis is obtained by comparing its response to those associated to real three-dimensional (3D) arrangements. The computed stress-strain curves obtained with two axisymmetric unit cell models having 100% ferrite and a 21% volume fraction of ferrite in the matrix, respectively, are shown in Fig. 3 along with the response of two equivalent 3D models. They are the cubic primitive (3DA) and cubic body-centered (3DB) cell arrangements, [10]. For the fully ferritic material there are no significant differences between axisymmetric and 3D FE models. In the case of the ferritic-pearlitic matrix, the behavior of the three models is again quite similar although the 3D models are apparently less stiff than the axisymmetric model. Nonetheless, the limited difference observed in Fig. 3 supports the use of the axisymmetric 2D model.

Fig. 3: a) Stress-strain curves for a full ferritic matrix and a ferritic/pearlitic matrix obtained using 3D- and axisymmetric 2D-FE model; b) 3D FE models

A direct comparison between axisymmetric unit cell modeling and experiments in terms of constitutive stress-strain response is presented in Fig. 4. The predicted behaviors are obtained for the volume fractions that characterize the microstructures of Fig. 1. The unit cell model with a low ferrite content (i.e. $\psi_F = 19.5\%$ and $\psi_G = 9.1\%$) as Fig. 2c, provides a close match with the corresponding microstructure (i.e. bull's eye structure of Fig. 2a). The computed stress-strain response (i.e. $\Sigma_2 - E_2$) fits the experimental tensile test curve quite well. The experimental stress-strain curves for the different ferrite/pearlite ratio of the matrix, Fig. 1b and 1c, are also shown in Fig. 4 as continuous lines. The correlation, satisfactory for a mainly pearlitic matrix, is found to increasingly deviate when the volume fraction of ferrite increases. The comparison of predicted vs. experimental stress-strain curves shows an overestimating trend of the actual material stress response as the ferrite volume fraction increases. A source of deviation between prediction and experiments could be the assumption of uniform nodule size and spacing of the present and previous studies [3,6-8] of nodular cast iron. These results,

while promising, motivate also the investigation of alternative modeling approach to predict microstructure-affected constitutive behavior.

Fig. 4: Experimental stress-strain curves compared to axisymmetric unit cell model predictions

MICROSTRUCTURAL FINITE ELEMENT APPROACH

Recently, a growing activity has been devoted to the development of micromechanical models of material response, especially for materials of a complex structure such as particle-reinforced metal matrix composites (MMC). The aim is an understanding of the origin of the material performance and the identification of optimized microstructures, [11]. In this framework the finite element method is frequently used as a tool for determining the link between microstructure and macroscopic response. The finite element analysis provides the global constitutive law that describes the relation between macroscopic stresses and strains defined as volumetric averages of the relevant microscopic stresses and strains variables. In the previous section the assumption of a regular array of equal-sized and equal-spaced graphite nodules is a potential shortcoming of the unit cell approach because a significant effect on the material response is expected from the heterogeneity of the matrix microstructure within the material volume. Direct inspection of the etched microstructures of Fig. 1 shows for example that the graphite nodule distribution is irregular.

An alternative approach developed for investigating the tensile behavior of nodular cast iron is based on the direct modeling of an actual microstructure, i.e. starting from etched micrographs such as those of Fig. 1. The steps are: 1) the magnified image of the microstructure is obtained by metallographic methods; 2) the digital image is transformed into a geometrical model made of distinct constitutive areas; 3) the geometrical model is meshed using 2D plane strain finite elements, 4) appropriate stress-strain laws of the constituent materials are introduced. Fig. 5 shows three microstructural models of nodular cast iron characterized by different ferrite/pearlite ratios and where graphite nodules are omitted.

Fig. 5: Window models of local nodular cast iron microstructures: a) ferritic matrix; b) ferritic/pearlitic matrix; c) mainly pearlitic matrix

Since the microstructural finite element model is aimed at providing the macroscopic (global) stress-strain material response, i.e. as for an ideal infinite medium subjected to uniform boundary conditions, different definitions of boundary conditions have been proposed, [7]. In the present study both continuity and periodicity have been enforced by appropriate boundary conditions on the boundary. In this way the finite element model is completely defined and the computational solution in the elastic plastic regime was sought iteratively. Modeling issues inherent to the approach are not discussed here for sake of brevity, [7].

Fig. 6: Von Mises stress distribution for the microstructural models of Fig. 5

Fig. 6 presents the Von Mises equivalent stress distribution if the three microstructural models of Fig. 5 at the same level of applied strain in the horizontal direction. The stress heterogeneity is affected by the microstructure with local concentration due to geometrical discontinuities (i.e. cavities) and stress gradients at material discontinuities (i.e. boundaries between pearlite and ferrite). The deformation is strongly localized along a 45-deg direction (i.e. suitably aligned cavities) in Fig. 6a, which is characterized by a homogeneous matrix. In Fig. 6b a stress concentration occurs in a narrow pearlitic ligament bridging two ferritic areas. Fig. 6c shows a highly heterogeneous stress distribution, although the bull's eye ferrite around the nodules, i.e. Fig. 2a, is subjected to a nearly uniform stress. The stress micro field in pearlite is disturbed by the presence of different size nodules.

The macroscopic stress-strain response of the finite element model is obtained by suitable averaging of the microscopic stress and strain distributions. In the presence of an applied direct macroscopic strain E_{11} (in the horizontal direction of Fig. 6) directly applied to the boundaries, the macroscopic normal stress Σ_{11} is determined as

$$\Sigma_{11} = \frac{1}{A} \sum_n F_1^{(n)} \quad (3)$$

where F_1 are the n nodal forces acting on the boundary and A is the cross-sectional area. The stress-strain responses obtained from the microstructural models with periodic boundary conditions up to 3% of deformation are shown in Fig. 7. A comparison with the companion response of equivalent (i.e. same graphite volume fraction and matrix structure) axisymmetric unit cell models of the previous section indicates always a stiffer behavior of the axisymmetric unit cell model because it is not affected by severe discontinuities and strain localizations associated to the heterogeneous phase arrangement of the microstructural models.

Fig. 7: Influence of the modeling approach on the stress-strain behavior of the three nodular cast irons of Fig. 1

CONCLUSIONS

The constitutive response of nodular cast iron having different microstructure has been modeled by different micromechanical approaches: i) an axisymmetric unit cell model and ii) a microstructural finite element model. The main conclusions of this study are:

- Both models predict the change of mechanical response of nodular cast iron as a function of the ferrite-to-pearlite ratio in the matrix.
- Direct correlation of predicted and experimental stress-strain curves showed an increasing overestimate of the material response with an increasing ferrite content in the matrix.
- The microstructural finite element model demonstrates the presence of strain localization phenomena also observed in the real materials.
- The mechanical response of the axisymmetric unit cell model is stiffer than that of an equivalent microstructural finite element model.

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